

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION OF THE ORIGIN AND QUALITY OF BARYTES IN THE TSARETA-TUNGAN KUDAKU AREA, NORTH WESTERN NIGERIA BASEMENT COMPLEX, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

A preliminary study of the baryte occurrence in the Tsareta-Tungan Kudaku area, Northwestern Nigeria shows that it is hosted by low- grade metamorphic rocks mainly Phyllites, in veins of about 1.5km wide and 4m deep. It is a fissure filling vein type deposited in fissures running parallel-sub parallel to the Anka fault system. The barytes has variable specific gravity ranging between 3.8 for surface occurrences and 4.3 at deeper levels. This quality meets the specification of specific gravity of 4.2 for use as drilling mud in the oil industry. Chemically, the baryte has BaSO₄ concentration between 79.1%-95.8%. The presence of an inclusion of pyrite and leached capping (gossans) which is typical of sulphides suggests that the hydrothermal fluids that formed the gold mineralization in the Anka region could be responsible for the formation of the baryte in the area.

KEYWORDS; Baryte, Tsareta-Tungan, Anka Fault, Vein, hydrothermal.

INTRODUCTION

Baryte, as an industrial mineral, is a major type of inert volume and weight filler in drilling mud used in the oil industry, in the chemical industry, as a constituent in lithophone paint as well as in the glass and paper industry. Most of the baryte mineralizations in Nigeria are reportedly found as vein occurrences within the middle Benue Trough with most concentration in the Azara, Awe and Keana areas, McCurry(2000), Offodile,(1980). The baryte deposits are usually found to be closely associated with Lead and Zinc and can be related to the same mineralizing activity. Baryte mineralizations have also been reported in Akpet area, Oban Massif in Southeastern Nigeria (Akpeke at al ,2006). Other occurrences are found in Gombe, Zurak, Akwana, Abakaliki and Ishiagu. It is significant to note that it is only in the middle Benue Trough that vein mineralization includes fluorite and baryte, Omada and Ike, (1996)

This paper reports on preliminary investigation on the origin, geochemistry and quality of a new baryte occurrence found within the metamorphic rocks of Anka Schist belt of the Basement complex of Northwestern Nigeria in contrast to the occurrences reported within the Cretaceous Benue Trough. The quality of the barite is here studied based on international specifications such as concentration of BaSO₄ (between 92-95%), degree of whiteness and reflectance, Specific gravity (4.2 and above), and concentration of iron oxide minerals, moisture and other foreign elements (less than 2-3%) (Dawson, 1985)

GEOLOGIC SETTING

Tsareta-Tungan Kudaku area falls within the Anka Schist belt in the Basement Complex of Northwestern Nigeria. (fig.1)

The Basement Complex includes all rocks older than the late Proterozoic metasediments. The geology of the Basement Complex in Nigeria have been described and reviewed by various authors including Ajibade,(1980),McCurry and Wright,(1976); Oyawoye,(1972) ;Rahaman (1976); Reyment (1976).

The Tsareta Tungan Kudaku area, however comprises of the mafic-ultramafic rocks(Diorites,Syenite,Gabbro); Molasse-type clastic sedimentary rocks, (unmetamorphosed greywackes and conglomerates); Older Granites ; Metasediments and Granite –gneiss. The Serpentinities are however the most extensive rocks in the study area.

METHOD OF STUDY

A total of twenty samples of baryte, and five each of host Phyllite and Serpentinite rocks were collected during the field work. The baryte samples were collected at various depths in veins which follows a structural trend of N18°E

corresponding to the major structural control exhibited by the Serpentinities emplaced at the margins of the Anka fault system, Ogezi (1977). The specific gravity of the baryte was also determined. However, only six representative samples of the baryte and one each of serpentinite and Phyllite were pulverized and analyzed for preliminary assessment of some of their major and trace element compositions using the energy dispersive X-rays fluorescence method at the Centre for Energy Research and training Zaria, Nigeria.

Fig. 1 Showing Sketch Geological Map of Study Area

RESULTS

Mode of Occurrence

The baryte mineralization in the area is hosted by the country rock (Phyllites) in veins of about 1.5m wide and 4m deep. The veins follow a general structural trend of N18°E which corresponds to the major direction of the serpentinite in the area and falls within the Anka fault system (AFS). They can therefore be described as fissure filling deposit type where hydrothermal solutions deposited or precipitated the baryte minerals in the fissures running parallel to the major Anka fault system (AFS).

The baryte veins occur approximately two Kilometers from the serpentinite bodies. At the time of this study, two veins were being mined and the veins appear on the surface as dykes occurring in close association with quartzites which also occur in the area. There were observed leached cappings (gossan) around the veins which is typically associated with sulphide mineralisation on top of the baryte veins.

Table 1. Specific Gravity of the Tsareta -Tungan Kudaku barytes.

Sample No.	Specific Gravity
TB1	3.80
TB2	4.10
TB3	4.40
TB4	4.35
TB5	4.30
TB6	4.25
AVERAGE VALUE	4.20

Chemical Properties

The baryte in the area has variable specific gravity ranging from 3.8-4.3. The least specific gravity of 3.8 was found at the top most regions of the trench where it was observed to be mostly weathered. However, those found at the deeper levels of the trench gave specific gravity values of between 4.1- 4.4. This falls within the specification in the oil industry (Table 1) required for use as drilling mud which is 4.2. Pyrite was observed as an impurity in the baryte.

The specific gravity of baryte is of considerable importance in determining its quality and use in the oil industry. Barytes with specific gravity values of 4.5 and above is considered pure while barytes with specific values from 4.2 satisfies the weight requirements of most oil industries. Apart from the barytes found at the top-most region of the trench, which gave specific gravity value of 3.8, those that occur at the deeper levels of the trench gave average values 4.20 which confirms good quality and thus suitable for use as a drilling mud.

Table 2. Chemical composition of the Tsareta -Tungan Kudaku barytes.

Sample no.	Concentration (%)					
	VEIN A		VEIN B		VEIN C	
	TB1	TB2	TB3	TB4	TB5	TB6
Al ₂ O ₃	0.94	0.54	1.06	0.90	1.36	0.87
SiO ₂	1.00	1.09	0.97	1.20	1.18	2.1
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.85	0.52	0.25	0.21	6.27	3.97
CaO	0.12	1.82	1.69	0.11	1.28	0.12
MnO	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
BaSO ₄	88.02	83.0	92.4	95.8	79.1	89.2
TiO ₄	1.30	0.87	1.56	1.40	1.98	1.07
SrO	0.54	0.99	0.23	0.23	1.00	0.39
As ₂ O ₃	0.01	0.03	0.03	ND	ND	0.01

Table 3 Results of geochemical analysis of host rocks of the baryte mineralization.

ELEMENTS	CONCENTRATIONS %	
Major oxides	SERPENTINITE	PHYLLITE
K ₂ O	1.494	2.591
Ca O	0.979	0.90
TiO ₂	0.756	0.923
MnO	13.82	0.067
Fe ₂ O ₃	7.08	7.460
Trace Elements	Conc. in ppm	Conc. in ppm
Ba	4.05 X 10 ⁴	1.12 X 10 ⁴
Ce	5.12 X 10 ¹	3.9 X 10 ¹
Zn	2.75 X 10 ²	1.16 X 10 ²
Pb	3.47 X 10 ²	6.78 X 10 ¹
Br	2.05 X 10 ¹	1.84 X 10 ¹
Rb	1.58 X 10 ¹	6.37 X 10 ¹
Sr	2.76 X 10 ²	7.5 X 10 ¹
Y	2.97 X 10 ¹	1.41 X 10 ¹
Zr	1.14 X 10 ²	1.31 X 10 ²
Nb	1.02 X 10 ¹	7.95 X 10 ⁰

The results of the chemical analyses of the baryte samples and the host rocks are presented in tables 2 and 3 respectively. The concentrations of BaSO₄ in the six samples preliminarily investigated ranged between 79.1 to 95.8% (Table 2). The SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ concentrations also varies between 1.0-2.1 and 0.54-1.36 % respectively while the Fe₂O₃ varied between 0.21-6.27%. However, it should be noted that the barytes with high BaSO₄ concentration tend to have low Fe₂O₃.

Chemically, the analyzed baryte gave a composition of between 79.1 to 95.8% BaSO₄. (Table 2). Also, texturally, in terms of colour, it was observed that most of the barytes is off-white especially the ones occurring close to the surface of the trench while those at the deeper levels where almost whitish in colour. This suggests that the pure Baryte samples occur at the deeper levels

ORIGIN

The baryte deposits in the Tsareta-Tungan Kudaku area is best described as vein or fissure filling deposit type where hydrothermal solutions precipitated the baryte minerals in the fissures running parallel-subparallel to the major Anka fault system (A.F.S). Previous studies of the origin of the Pan-African mesothermal gold mineralization of Bin Yauri, Garba, (1996) using isotopes showed that sulphur isotopes have positive values of $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ which is considered to be consistent with a crustal sedimentary sulphur source. Also, carbon isotopic studies, Garba and Akande, (1992) gave values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ to be in the order of $-7 \pm 2\%$ which reflects the average crustal carbon(C) value of -7% [8]. Garba and Akande, (1992), Obtained values in the order of $13 \pm 1.4\%$ for hydrothermal carbonates at Bin Yauri. These values fall within the range for metamorphic water, Craw and Chamberlain, (1996) and are markedly different from the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ associated with magmatic or normal meteoric waters.

Thus, from isotopic studies, it could be inferred that a reservoir confined to the clastic sedimentary rock may be the source of the mineralizing fluids generated through large scale metamorphic process along an active transcurrent Anka fault during the waning stages of the Pan-African event, Hoefs, (1987). The heat of the metamorphism which resulted in the regional metamorphism of the entire area and the intrusion of the Pan-African granitoids could have provided the heat needed for the generation of the mineralizing fluid.

The host rock (Phyllite, Schist) and the surrounding basement rocks are possibly the source from which these elements were leached. This is attested to by the high barium concentration of 1.12×10^4 and 4.05×10^4 in the phyllites and serpentinites respectively (Table 3). The baryte has a barium concentration of 4.5×10^5 to 5.5×10^5 showing that only a concentration factor of 10 is needed for a barite deposit to form using these rocks as source. Fairly noticeable concentrations of lead and Zinc in the serpentinites and phyllites as well as baryte shows a possibility of the mineralizing fluids carrying sulphur species of lead-Zinc hence the area has the potentials of Pb-Zn mineralization which is common with most of the barite occurrences in Nigeria.

The probable pathway for the fluids is the major Anka fault system. This fault system has been severally been described as a possible crustal suture, Ajibade, (1980); McCurry and Wright, (1976)

These fluids are believed to be transported through the late tectonic fault zone into smaller suture or fissures formed as a result of the brittle fault zone within the Phyllites.

These fluids moved through these faults to the near surface which is characterized by low temperatures and pressures thus favouring precipitation.

CONCLUSIONS

From the discussion above the following conclusions can be drawn:

The baryte in the Tsareta-Tungan Kudaku area can be described as a fissure filling deposit type formed by deposition of hydrothermal solutions in the fissure running parallel-subparallel to the major Anka fault system.

The baryte is of high quality and is suitable for use as drilling mud.

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The source of the ore elements could be from the leaching of these elements from the surrounding basement rocks.

Future research would be on isotopic studies of the barytes to confirm deductions on the origin.

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REFERENCES

- Ajibade, A.C.,1980. Geotectonic Evolution of the Zungeru region , Nigeria PhD dissertation ,University of Wales, Aberystwyth
- Ajibade, A.C.and Wright,J.B.,1989. The Togo-Benin-Nigeria Shield;Evidence of crustal aggregation in the Pan-African belt, Tectonophysics,165 125-129.
- Akpeke, G. B.; Ekwueme, B. N. and Ephraim, B. E., 2006. The nature and origin of the Barite mineralization in Akpet area, Oban Massif, Southeastern Nigeria. Journal of Geological Sciences, Vol.4 No.2 139-146
- Craw, D.and Chamberlain,C. P., 1996. Meteoric incursion and oxygen fronts in the Dalaradian metamorphic belt, southwest Scotland: a new hypothesis for regional gold mobility. Mineralium Deposita 31,365-373
- Dawson, K.R. 1985. Geology of Ba, Sr, and Fl. Deposits in Canada. Geological Survey of Canada, Econ. Geol. Rept., 34. 1-30
- Garba, I., 1996. Tourmalinization related to late proterozoic Early palaeozoic lode gold mineralisation in the Bin Yauri area, Nigeria mineralium Deposita.31,201-209
- Garba, I. and Akande ,S.O, 1992. The origin and significance of non-aqueous CO₂ fluid inclusions in the non aqueous veins of Bin Yauri, northwestern Nigeria. Mineralium Deposita 27,249-25
- Hoefs, J., 1987. Stable isotope Geochemistry. Springer-Verlag, New York, 241p.
- Kogbe, A.C. 1989. Geology of Nigeria. Elizabethan Publishing Company Lagos Nigeria
- Mangs, A.D. 2000.The viability of setting up a Baryte processing Pilot plant in Mabudi Langtang south L.G.A Plateau State. Unpublished M.Sc Research Seminar University of Jos.
- McCurry, P., 2000. The geology of the Precambrian to Lower Palaeozoic rocks of northern Nigeria- a review, in: Kogbe, C.A(ED), Geology of Nigeria. Elizabethan Publication Company Lagos.
- McCurry, P. and J.B.Wright,J.B., 1976. Geochemistry of calc- alkaline volcanics in Northwestern Nigeria, and a possible Pan-African suture zone. Earth Planetary Science Letter 37, 90-96.
- Omada, J. I. and Ike, E. C., 1996. On the economic appraisal of the barite mineralization and saline springs in the middle Benue trough, Nigeria. J. Min. Petr. Econ. Geol. 91, 109-115
- Offodile, M.E., 1980. A Mineral Survey of the Cretaceous of the Benue Valley, Nigeria. Cretaceous Research 1, 101-124
- Ogezi, A.E., 1977. Geochemistry and geochronology of basement rocks from Northwestern Nigeria. PhD dissertation, University of Leeds.

Ogezi, A. E., 1978. Geochemistry and Origin of ensialic Alpine type Serpentinite Associations from Mallam Tanko (Shemi) and Ribah (Wasagu), NW Nigeria. In Dessuvie et. al (Eds), African Geology ; Nigeria. 67-99

Onyeagocha, A. C., 1979. The Mallam Tanko Serpentinite Petrology and Economic Implication, Jour. Mining and Geology 16(1)37-40

Oyawoye, A., 1972. The Basement Complex of Nigeria. In Dessuvie et. al (Eds). African Geology ; Nigeria. 67-99.

Rahaman, M. A. 1976. Review of the Basement Geology of S-W Nigeria. in C.A. Kogbe, Elizabethan Publishing Company Lagos Nigeria
42-58

Reyment, R. A. 1976. Aspects of the geology of Nigeria Ibadan University press.

Wright , J.B., 1976. Fracture systems in Nigeria and initiation of fracture zones in the south Atlantic, Tectonophysics 34 43-47

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